

Drum seeders - flexibility for modern nurseries

In-line filling and seeding systems have traditionally been large, robust items of equipment. In particular, large compressors and vacuum pumps were necessary. New concepts and use of latest control equipment technology have reduced the need for this large, expensive equipment.

During sowing, seeds of less than one gram are moved only a short distance during sowing. This does not require heavy equipment. The Hamilton Drum Seeder takes this into account.

The most noticeable difference between a Hamilton Drum Seeder and other drum seeders is the size of the drum itself. The new small-format drums are possible through advanced stepper motor design that overcomes the problem of the drum having to do

The Hamilton Drum Seeder is an extremely versatile machine suited to the wide range of sowing requirements typical of major nurseries. These machines are supplied and serviced by Transplant Systems of Melbourne and Christchurch.

one revolution per tray. These drums are controlled by intelligent circuitry that allows the drum surface to move at the same speed as that of the tray.

Removing the link between the tray length and drum diameter added another benefit. Each drum has a duplex hole pattern. This allows two different hole sizes for different seed sizes, or even two completely different hole configurations to cope with different tray models. Not only are the smaller drums more economical to make and buy, the duplex method cuts in half the number of drums needed.

Small format drums offer other advantages in terms of sowing performance and vacuum pump

requirements. The small volume inside the drum allows a triple stage sowing process to be used. A vacuum picks up the seed, low air pressure releases the seed and compressed air purges the holes for continuous, trouble-free operation. This ensures consistent accuracy in seed pick-up and placement, with minimal operator error. Seed placement in the cell can be set to within one millimetre.

A small vacuum pump is easily able to cope with the vacuum requirements of these new style drums, even over extended seeding runs. This is a cost saving, without any loss in performance. The overall smaller size of the machine and its power requirements means greater flexibility in placement. A 2-metre conveyor, dibbler and seed covering hopper, with standard electrical and compressed air connections, are all that is required. This facilitates using the filling machine for non-seeding applications such as setting cuttings and plugs.

Sophisticated circuitry and use of space-age materials does not mean a complex and difficult-to-use machine. Drums are very easily changed, vacuum control is easy and accurate for optimal seed pick up and singulation. The use of twin air curtains makes for an exceptionally easy to use and accurate seeder. Speed of sowing is generally limited only by the rate at which trays can be supplied to the seeder. Lannen 144 and 256 trays are easily sown in less than 4 seconds.

A small seed pick-up surface on the drum allows accurate sowing to the last few seeds. This is very important where expensive seed is being used, and especially so where smaller runs are being done. Extra seed is quickly and easily removed by a vacuum cleaner into a jar for storage.

The Hamilton Drum Seeder design has resulted in a highly versatile machine suited to a wide range of nursery businesses. The inflexibility of the large-format drums restricts them to only large scale seeding operations. The smaller scale of the Hamilton Drum Seeder is now recognised as a preferred seeder for short and extended serious sowing requirements.

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Field planting - extending the options

The versatile RT-2 field transplanter from Lannen is constantly being improved. This semi-automatic transplanter has proven itself internationally, and particularly in both Australia and New Zealand, operating extremely well with the local soil conditions and planting requirements.

A range of frame options is now available as standard to suit just about any vegetable seedling requirement. Adding a dual toolbar is now the most likely choice for the popular two-row configuration. As can be seen in the photograph, the rear toolbar carries the planters and has a free run for positioning the planters quickly and accurately anywhere along it. The front toolbar is not normally altered after commissioning, and carries the land support wheels and three point linkage.

A standard three metre toolbar also allows the positioning of a third row, offset from the rest of the machine. This option is becoming increasingly popular for mixed vegetable farms where two and three-row beds have to be planted regularly. The standard two-row configuration is used for two-row planting. For three-row planting, the toolbar is positioned off-centre, with two units positioned to plant the row directly behind the tractor and the third unit positioned to plant the centre row of the bed to one side.

Instead of changing the position of planters and the toolbar relative to the tractor, another option is to use the semi-tandem frame. RT-2 planters are normally only able to be positioned for 19 inches between rows, but with the semi-tandem frame, 15 inch spacing is possible. Two-row planting is still easy to do by slipping the centre unit out of the frame. The

Versatile Lannen RT-2 semi-automatic field transplanters in a two-row configuration. Note the free movement possible on the second toolbar allowing accurate positioning of the rows without interference with the three-point hitch.

A semi-tandem frame allows closer spacing of RT-2 units than is normally possible on a single toolbar. Note the new rubber-tyred rollers attached to the RT-2 units themselves.

semi-tandem frame allows a relatively small tractor to cope with the machines, while not having to extend the toolbars across two beds. This is a useful feature for coping with narrow headlands.

Many soil types are easier to plant into if the soil immediately ahead of the planter is rolled. Earlier versions of rollers were large steel rollers attached with their own floating framework. The new rollers are treadless tyres fitted to the planter itself, thus reducing the overall weight of the units on the toolbar while retaining the free floating nature by floating the roller with the planter.

Cost savings with booms

A uniform crop, with repeatable results from one planting to the next, cannot be achieved without uniform and timely irrigation. Achieving this uniformity of watering is difficult, and manual methods require years of experience to detect minute changes in plant growth before they become too variable. Boom irrigators offer an extremely uniform water application pattern.

In addition to plant uniformity, boom irrigators are typically 90% efficient in their water application, compared with 50% for most hand watering applications. There is clearly a considerable saving in water, and nutrients where these are applied with the water.

Saving water and growing better nursery plants can be achieved using irrigation booms. The most recent technology and design concepts are proving their worth. Simple, progressive design principles make the unit quite feasible for user installation, cutting the costs by offering the booms as kitsets. Installation can also be arranged.

Booms can be transferred from bay to bay or house to house. This allows the investment to be maximised over a larger

growing area. Coupled with the labour, water and fertiliser savings common to boom systems, these savings allow most growers to pay for the system within one year.

Greenhouse irrigation booms, supplied and installed in Australia and New Zealand by Transplant Systems, offer growers a major advance in their automation and mechanisation programme, while at the same time reducing water usage and improving plant quality through more even application.

A range of models and optional items is available. Fully computer-programmable models are available, but the simpler linear programming on the boom will prove best for many nurseries. Linear programming allows the boom to follow a preset series of operations, including different rates of water application, skipping sections of the benches, and automatic start and stop functions.

The booms are able to travel at variable speeds, set independently for forward and reverse operations, suspended from rails fixed to the greenhouse trusses. The hose and power cord can be looped or fully suspended in a patented hose carriage to keep them completely clear of the aisles. This Centre Feed handling method uses half the hose and cord necessary for the looped end-feed method.

House widths of up to 15m and lengths of 60m are within the standard specifications. Double this length is possible using the Centre Feed hose handling method. Unusually low truss heights can be accommodated, and the boom height can be adjusted according to the crop to be watered.

Single-rail and outside irrigation booms are also part of the range. The outside booms are not suspended and booms can be 18m wide. Nozzles for watering, fertigation or misting can be fitted on any of the booms, with an option to apply fungicides using a boom-mounted proportioner. This reduces the amount of pipe to be flushed after spraying. Multiple nozzle bodies can be fitted allowing a quick change of nozzle according to requirements. Collision, boom twist and loss of water pressure are standard safety features.

Simple, reliable irrigation booms offer enormous benefits over traditional hand watering and fixed sprinkler systems. Contact Transplant Systems today and get your watering methods under control.

Transplant Systems steps up activities in Australia

Responding to increased demand for equipment and services, the Australian office has moved to larger premises in Berwick, Melbourne. This move increases warehousing space considerably and positions the Company better in preparing for the introduction of automated plant nursery and field planting methods.

Australian nurseries and commercial vegetable growers are increasingly utilising the benefits of the latest automation and mechanisation technology available. This move to larger premises reflects this interest and demand for nursery and field planting equipment.

Finland hosts forest research congress

A IUFRO (International Union of Forest Research Organisations) congress is only held every five years. The 1995 congress attracted some 3000 foresters from 95 countries to Finland. Containerised plant raising techniques was of considerable interest as evidenced by the pre-IUFRO meeting titled "Afforestation of first rotation sites" which dealt extensively with nursery systems and their impact on forest establishment. Lannen Plant Systems was able to demonstrate their range of Plantek forestry trays, including plants of the silver beech, an important source of fibre for high-quality pulp in Finland.

The Pottiputki transplanting tube is the easiest, fastest and most efficient way to plant any type of containerised seedling. It is extensively used for forestry plantings, as well as cut flower crops and market gardening.

NTV '96 trade exhibition

This major horticultural trade exhibition in Holland is regarded as an important venue to monitor developments and releases of new nursery technology. Colin Purchase of Transplant Systems, New Zealand visited NTV 1996. While at NTV, Colin met up with a number of Australian nursery visitors, all busy planning major expansions in their nursery facilities.

John and Jackie Thirkettle of Thirkettle Nurseries, Nelson with their new Mayer potting machine fitted to a tractor-drawn trailer and complete with fertiliser dispenser. This machine was installed by Transplant Systems Limited of Christchurch., New Zealand.

Australian Forest Nursery Tour

During March 1996 more than 70 Australian and New Zealand forest nursery staff attended the nursery tour and conference of the Australian Forest Nursery Association visiting nurseries in Queensland.

A particular feature of this tour was the opportunity for frank and open discussions about technical aspects of tree propagation. While clearly the bare-root system of propagation is going to remain a dominant method in the industry, a large number of nursery managers noted that containerisation of propagation was becoming a significant part of their future expansion.

Michael Brooke and Warrick Nelson of Transplant Systems attended the tour to improve their understanding of forest nursery requirements, particularly taking into account the interest in containerisation and use of Lannen side-slot air-pruning technology in containers. These containers are

increasingly being specified for tree propagation, particularly the most important plantation species of *Pinus radiata* and *Eucalyptus nitens*.

New forestry investment

*The Lannen FL-2 filling machine is preferred for major new forest nursery investments. The Forestry Corporation of New Zealand Limited took delivery of the third machine in New Zealand. Forenza and Hill Nurseries installed their systems in 1994 and 1995. This machine will be used for containerised fascicle cutting propagation of *Pinus radiata*.*

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